

THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS FRENCH LESSONS.

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Annotation: French language is a foreign language in Uzbekistan and that its teaching and learning cannot take the same process as acquiring first or a second language. In order to be able to interact with the native speakers in real life day to day communication, several techniques and methods should be used. Among French language learning methods, the leading position is occupied by the communicative approach, which is aimed directly at the development of communication.

Keywords: communicative method, French language, grammar, communicative technique, communication skills, listening, reading, speaking.

The communicative method of teaching foreign language is recognized as the most effective all over the world, and today many university teachers work on its basis. The basis of the communicative technique is the study of language through situations of communication. Communicative method is a combination of traditional and intensive methods, but with a number of its own characteristics. This method helps to overcome the language barrier, relieves a person from the fear of speaking in a foreign language. Most of the popular French training courses demonstrate the benefits of this method. In the classroom, students have the opportunity to use the language in real life situations. The concept of a communicative technique consists of the constant development of the main skills required to master any foreign language (reading, grammar, speaking, listening and writing). The ultimate and key goal is to learn student's basic communication skills in French. Mastering the required material in a short time and with an impressive degree of consolidation is due to the fact that the key expressions of the French language, grammatical structures, vocabulary are conveyed to the student in the form of a real and emotionally colored situation. Since the primary and fundamental manifestation of any language is found in oral speech and being the first manifestation of communication, acquiring oral communication competence in a foreign language like French is essential. The oral communication class therefore helps the students improve their speaking skill and to acquire and put into practice the elementary principles of interpersonal communication. Let us consider the learning process of French using communicative method. Classes are held in a relaxed environment. Communication takes place only in a foreign language. Teacher explains new rules, words using familiar vocabulary, grammatical constructions, gestures, facial expressions, drawings and other visual aids. Role-playing games and dramatization are very effective at the initial stage of learning. Dramatization - presentation in the form of scenes, fairy tales, stories, as well as plot pictures. Everyday situations are played out: acquaintance, choice of travel route, congratulations, shopping, and so on. The game provides an emotional impact on language learners, activates hidden capabilities of a person. It facilitates the acquisition of knowledge, skills, abilities,

creates conditions for the active mental activity of its participants. All its participants are equal, even the weakest are not shy due to the feeling of equality. If a participant in a role-playing game does not know a word, he always has the opportunity to replace it with any other. Statement of the problem Most French classes are dominated by written work and little or no attention is given to oral work. Even during the class titled Oral Expression almost only written work is done and in English or the mother tongue too. This does not give the learners the possibility of developing the necessary competences for oral comprehension and production. Although the current French curriculum in the National Commission for Colleges of Education minimum standard, insists on the use of the communicative approach, the traditional method is still in practice by some colleagues in our French classes in the colleges of education. In communicative technique, emphasis is placed on the active use of audio recordings, interactive materials and videos. A variety of methodological techniques used in the development of French using communicative method makes it possible to form skills required by a modern person in his business and everyday life, namely ability to negotiate, make presentations, make reports, make calls by phone, Skype and other modern means of communication, to correspond with interlocutor in colloquial and business French. Use of the native language in communicative classes between students and the teacher is highly undesirable, often even forbidden. For the purpose of explaining meanings of new words teacher and students refer to previously known words, expressions, photographs, slides, drawings, gestures, facial expressions, video clips. For films, songs, newspapers, TV shows, magazines, comics are used to achieve the goal, so students are gradually immersed in culture of France, learn important and interesting facts from history, get acquainted with the geography of this country. Educational games are also effective, including board games (for example, Scrabble). Thanks to visual and entertaining materials, learning French becomes quite exciting. Teaching listening comprehension or semantic perception (understanding) of speech by ear involves students performing exercises to form general auditory skills, speech exercises and subsequent work with audio text. While teaching French as a foreign language, the setting of the learning goal is carried out with a focus on a certain level of development of communicative competence, which may be different for its elements: basic in reading and writing, elementary in listening. At the initial stage of training, the student operates with units of communication, which are gradually integrated into more extensive speech actions.

Thus, the improvement of the skill is carried out by the followings: a) through its transfer to another communicative situation b) on a more complex type of text c) with the inclusion of new language material. The psychological features of this speech activity determine the requirements for the method of teaching listening:

1. There is a need for motivation for listening, that is, interest that helps to maintain the attention of listeners (students).
2. The task of deciphering sound information is simplified if the listener is initially oriented and well acquainted with the situation to which this information relates (the teacher's attitude, illustrations, etc.), i.e., it is about anticipating the probable content of the text.
3. Listening should be preceded by instructions, the main purpose of which is to form the listener's mindset on the nature of perception and understanding of information. The installation should differ depending on the task that is set for the audience. The means of training students in understanding of sounding speech is to teach them the optimal methods of listening to the text. This is a general listening, without any notes that distract from

understanding, at the first presentation of the text and, on the contrary, keeping notes when listening again.

4. The text should be presented in such a volume and at a pace that corresponds to the level and educational capabilities of the students.

5. While hearing a foreign language, a backtrack is required. Therefore, the text for listening should be presented more than once. After the second listening, exercises are performed to determine the degree of understanding of the text by students. The third listening is offered for self-examination of correctness of the performance of various tasks: firstly, general understanding, then tasks to search for the given information, and finally, questions that require generalizations, conclusions. The act of communication arises against the background and under the influence of a set of circumstances. The linguistic and semantic characteristics of a speech act are determined by the conditions of both intralinguistic and extra linguistic nature, which are present at a certain moment of the speech act. These can be circumstances of both an external and an internal plan that are significant for a person at the moment: a phone call or a desire to receive an object that is beyond the easily accessible, a feeling of hunger or dissatisfaction with a person, a thought, desire, invitation, etc. expressed by someone. Due to it, a communicative situation is considered as the minimum cell of communication of the "molecule" of oral communication, which is "one of the contingent conditions for the emergence or successful implementation of a speech act." The communicative act is defined as "the sum of the statements of all communicants (retrospectively - the total text) of one communicative situation.

The role and position of the teachers are very important in the teaching of French because they can encourage or discourage the learners in their learning of the language. Unfortunately, there is a grave shortage of qualified teachers and teaching materials for the oral aspect of language learning. Therefore, we find that more than half of the learners are usually very badly taught or are never truly exposed to oral communication of the language. Most of the teachers use the traditional method or the grammar-translation method to teach their students which of course results in the poor performance of students, most especially in oral communication. This is because some of the teachers themselves are unable to communicate freely in French and as such resort to teaching solely in English or the mother tongue. Therefore, to be adequately qualified to teach especially a foreign language like French, one needs to be well trained pedagogically to be able to properly handle well the teaching of the subject. Overall, the teacher should be patient with especially the very timid students, as this will one of the factors to inspire and build up their confidence.

Another factor affecting learning process is teaching aids and materials. Textbooks and teaching aids of communicative methodology consist of practical tasks in the form of dialogues and topics for discussion, from non-adapted texts, exercises for translation are excluded. Such textbooks are usually accompanied by CDs with audio and video recordings. While working with new vocabulary, substitution exercises are used, logical riddles, replacement of transcriptions with words, puzzles. In textbooks aimed at developing communication skills, there are large number of photographs, drawings that illustrate texts and they serve as a basis for various kinds of tasks. Tutorials are level based; each section contains topics for working out material.

Conclusion and recommendations Universities that actively use the communicative methodology invite native speakers of French as teachers. On the one hand, a Frenchman

contributes to excellent pronunciation and understanding of a foreigner's oral speech by ear, acquaintance with the most common and modern colloquial vocabulary of the French language. On the other hand, it is often difficult for a native speaker to explain the meaning of certain words, as well as grammar that has no analogue in learner's native language, especially if the native speaker does not speak it at all. It is difficult for students to master grammar rules without explanation. The communicative technique does not provide an opportunity to develop writing skills. It is one of the drawbacks of communicative technique.

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